

Rethinking Face and Politeness

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This paper addresses the concepts of face and (im)politeness from both first-order and second-order perspectives, and attempts at rethinking face, (im)politeness, and Face-Threatening Acts (FTAs). It suggests that each and every speech act is issued as a result of the interplay between self's intention and his motivation, with intention being the ignition, and motivation the fuel. Listing a number of features of speech acts, the paper further argues that FTAs must be redefined, and suggests the existence of Face-Attacking Acts (FAAs) as well as Face-Guarding Acts (FGAs)—but uses FAAs as a cover term for both. The paper also suggests a model for the description of FAAs/FGAs, and argues that they fall into four classes: (1) self-destructive hypothetical FAAs, (2) self-/other-guarding hypothetical FGAs, (3) other-destructive objective FAAs, and (4) self-/other-guarding objective FGAs. It then goes on to rethink the concept of (im)politeness, and suggests a model for politeness theory which entails a redefinition of politeness and impoliteness. It provides colorful examples and tangible evidence to relate (im)politeness to both context and collective pragmatic competence, and claims that action can be dominant or recess to speech just like dominant versus recess genes in biology.

Keywords: Politeness; Impoliteness; Intentionality; Face Wants; Face-Threatening Acts (FTAs); Face-Attacking Acts (FAAs)

1. Introduction

Showing respect for other people's reputation or face is so important that almost all religions and faiths have strongly called for their believers' attention to this very important human quality. For one thing, it is claimed by most Shiite clerics that Ali bin Abi Talib, the first Shiite Imam, used to frequently remind his followers that vilifying others is even worse than shedding their blood. It is not strange to see that books by poets and writers in such ancient cultures as Iran (or Persia) are full of episodes that invite people to show respect for other people's reputation and face. The Persian term '*aberoo*' (pronounced as /a:bəru:/ which can literally be translated as 'water of face') is synonymous to the concept of face (Goffman, 1955), and even the phrase '*aberoo rizi kardan*' (pronounced as /a:bəru: ri:zi: kərdæn/ which literally means 'shedding the face water of other') is a metaphor that shows the similarity between vilifying or defaming others and shedding their

blood. An act of '*aberoo rizi kardan*' is on a par with ripping face from people. It seems as if *aberoo* is a kind of guise or mask or coating that people wear on their faces, and that, through *aberoo rizi kardan*, others try to rip off this mask, guise, or coating.

By way of contrast, the Persian word "*adab*" (pronounced as /ædæb/ and synonymous to 'politeness'), is the human quality that prevents people from attempts at *aberoo rizi kardan* or ripping off other people's faces. Although the main aim of *adab* or politeness is to create and maintain conditions in which people feel comfortable and relaxed, there are times at which politeness norms and formulas are manipulated so that shame is inflicted on certain individuals. Cornered in such situations, the inflicted individual strives to redress their face and to reset the situation to its previous normal relaxed state unless they choose to terminate the previous situation and create a whole-new situation without any relations with the vilifier or slanderer. One such situation is what is called '*ruberu kardan*' (pronounced as /ru:bəru: kærdæn/ and roughly synonymous to 'confrontation'). In *ruberu kardan*, the individual who believes others have been quoting a third party to vilify them summons both the vilifier and the third party, confronts both of them simultaneously, and asks for explanation and clarification. An act of *ruberu kardan* is paradoxical in that it is face-attacking/face-threatening and face-saving at the same. The face of the person who has been vilifying as well as that of the third party are attacked by the summoner. Based on the current literature on politeness, it is quite hard to decide if the summoner's act is an act of politeness or impoliteness. Using data from acts of *ruberu kardan*, *aberoo rizi kardan*, and various other instances of social interaction, the current paper addresses the concepts of face and (im)politeness from both first-order and second-order perspectives, and attempts at rethinking face and (im)politeness.

2. Politeness and Face

Although politeness was an area of interest for some linguists even before 1978 (cf., Lakoff, 1973), it was the pioneering formulation of politeness theory by Brown and Levinson in 1978 that paved the way for current studies and research in the field (Hickey and Stewart, 2005). Since 1978, politeness theory has gained a lot of popularity and has attracted a great deal of attention on the part of the academia. As stated by politeness theorists, politeness addresses the human quality that has to do with principles of appropriate social and cultural behavior (i.e., what has come to be known as etiquette). Notice that some people argue that politeness is not the same as etiquette (Mills, 2004; Sifianou & Tzanne, 2010).

Politeness can be treated as a fixed concept or an idea that embraces polite and appropriate social behavior within a culture. It can be seen as a set of

general principles that inform social life, and that are translated into being modest, generous, sympathetic, tactful, nice, and so forth; moreover, it can also be seen as specific tactics and procedures that structure each and every human interaction (Yule, 1996).

It is because of this dual nature of politeness that, while strongly influential, Brown and Levinson's politeness theory has attracted much criticism. For one thing, Grundy noted that "Much of our thinking about politeness is bedeviled by the fact that 'politeness' is a folk term" (2000, p. 164). What Grundy suggests is that the concept of politeness derives from two traditions. On the one hand, it has to do with good manners, social and conventional courtesy, and etiquette. On the other hand, it assumes the semblance of a professional term in the field of pragmatics. Grundy seems to suggest that Brown and Levinson should have coined a novel term instead of their 'politeness' theory.

Nevertheless, in their formulation of politeness theory, Brown and Levinson (1978) drew on the concept of 'face' first proposed by Goffman (1955), and even today it is clearly understood and widely accepted that any study or evaluation of politeness will have to engage the notion of face (Brown and Levinson, 1987) although some scholars believe that 'face' and 'politeness' should be disentangled (see, for example, Haugh (in press)) . Face is "the positive social value a person effectively claims for himself by the line others assume he has taken during a particular contact. Face is an image of self delineated in terms of approved social attributes" (Goffman, 1955, p. 213). It is "something that is emotionally invested, and that can be lost, maintained, or enhanced, and must be constantly attended to in interaction" (Brown and Levinson, 1978, p. 66). In general, people "cooperate (and assume each other's cooperation) in maintaining face in interaction, such cooperation being based on the mutual vulnerability of face" (Brown and Levinson, 1978, p. 66). Face means the "public self-image of a person. It refers to the emotional and social sense of self that one has and expects everyone else to recognize" (Yule, 1996, p. 60). Politeness is therefore defined as the tools, means, strategies, and tactics that people employ to show their awareness of their own and other people's faces. Closely related to the concept of face is the notion of 'face wants'. People have expectations concerning their public self-image (i.e., their self wants) and normally expect others to show respect for their face-wants and, in turn, show respect for others' face wants (Yule, 1996). Nevertheless, an act of *'aberoo rizi kardan'* is an example of a speech event via which the self disregards other's face and attacks it.

Needless to say, Brown and Levinson (1978) have expanded the concept of face and proposed two categories of for it: (a) positive, and (b) negative.

While negative face attests the fact that individuals keep their face by clearly showing that they do not intend to impose themselves on others (e.g., through mitigation and indirectness), positive face aims at establishing strong ties between individuals (e.g., by respecting other's desire to be liked, respected, or understood) (Salmani Nodoushan, 2007). Negative face, therefore, emphasizes other's rights and freedom whereas positive face cares about the self's esteem. As such, politeness is closely related to the negotiation and maintenance (and where needed, redress) of face in social encounters. Needless to say, individuals are normally expected to maintain one another's face in any social interaction; Brown and Levinson (1987) take face to be universal in that both positive and negative face are part and parcel of any human culture.

Nevertheless, human interaction is not always face-saving. There are situations where individuals' acts and speech become quite face-threatening; In fact, Brown and Levinson have claimed that most of our acts are face-threatening. Any act that can threaten interactants' face is a face-threatening act (FTA); it is an act that damages the face of the speaker (i.e., the self) or the hearer (i.e., other). It can either damage negative face or positive face; hence, negative versus positive face-threatening acts. Through negative face-threatening acts, addressee's freedom of action is breached and rules of politeness are flouted (although requests, for example, are FTAs even if they are mitigated). Positive FTAs, on the other hand, are acts through which the self shows their indifference to, or disapproval of, other's wishes and wants (Brown and Levinson, 1987; Salmani Nodoushan, 2006; Yule, 1996).

Both positive and negative FTAs cause damage to both the self and other. According to Brown and Levinson (1987), through negative FTAs, speakers interfere with the freedom of their hearers by (a) affirming or denying their hearers' future actions (e.g., making requests, giving orders, etc.), (b) expressing sentiments towards their hearers or their property (e.g., flattering, complimenting, etc.), or (c) promising some future action (e.g., making offers, promises, etc.). At the same time, negative FTAs also cause damage to speakers in that they force speakers to surrender to the power of their hearers (e.g., expressing thanks, accepting apologies, etc.). Positive FTAs, too, cause damage to both speakers and hearers. They cause damage to hearers by (a) showing speakers' disapproval of them (e.g., insults, accusations, etc.), or (b) showing their indifference towards hearers (e.g., interrupting, belittling, etc.). They can also cause damage to speakers by showing that the speakers themselves are not right (e.g., apologizing, confessions, self-humiliation, etc.).

In situations where face-threatening acts are inevitable or even desirable, speakers often resort to certain face-saving or politeness strategies which aim at saving their hearers' face (Salmani Nodoushan, 2008). Brown and Levinson

(1987) classified these strategies into five main categories: (a) bald on-record strategies, (b) positive politeness strategies which emphasize solidarity, (c) negative politeness strategies which emphasize others' freedom, (d) off-record/indirect strategies, and (e) "Don't do the FTA" strategy (Salmani Nodoushan, 2011). Bald on-record strategies are used when the self is in such close terms with other that no mitigation is needed; in such situations, speakers either do not make any attempt at minimizing the threat, or do so only implicitly. Through positive politeness strategies, speakers intentionally try to minimize threats to their hearers' positive face. By way of contrast, speakers draw on negative politeness strategies to avoid imposing themselves on their hearers. Finally, indirect/off-record strategies move the speakers away from situations in which there is the potential to be imposing. Any utterance that can insinuate an act on the part of the hearer is an example of off-record politeness strategies (Brown and Levinson, 1987).

3. Rethinking FTAs

It is taken for granted in most, if not all, human societies and populations that the 'self' should respect 'other' and care about other's face-wants. There are, however, certain occasions (both in terms of conversations and speech events) when people intentionally choose to break this tacit social convention and purposefully attack other's face (e.g., swearing, cursing, stigmatizing, vilifying, etc.). It is doubtful if the term 'face-threatening acts' can be used to precisely describe such occasions. Nevertheless, it should be remembered that "face is typically at risk when the self needs to accomplish something involving other" (Yule, 1996, p. 67); therefore, as the theory roughly claims, all speech acts are innately face-threatening—although 'congratulations' or 'wishes' in appropriate situations may not look like FTAs.

This said, what I would like to suggest here is that a distinction should be made between acts that are face-threatening (i.e., virtually all acts when seen in the light of Brown and Levinson's politeness theory) and acts that are face-attacking (i.e., certain intentional acts). While the self does not have any intention of ripping face from other in the former, they intentionally choose to attack other's face in the latter. I would therefore like to secure the phrase 'face-attacking acts (FAAs)' for this latter group of FTAs. There are, of course, expressions like 'face-aggravating acts' in the literature (c.f., Locher and Watts, 2008), but my approach to the issue is somewhat different. To me it seems that face-threatening and face-attacking acts (FTAs vs. FAAs) are in inclusional distribution of the "Q entails P" type where P stands for face-attacking acts and Q for face-threatening acts. In other words, if an act is face-attacking, it has to be face-threatening, but a face-threatening act does not

have to be face attacking. This relationship can be visualized as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Inclusional distribution of FTAs and FAAs.

In face-threatening acts, the threat is hidden inside the act itself; in face-attacking acts, on the other hand, the threat is hidden inside the act and, at the same time, the attack is hidden inside the intention of the self. What this distinction suggests is that threat is an attribute of all acts and part and parcel of them, and that attack is an attribute of the self or the agent/doer of face-attacking acts. Table 1 provides a reader-friendly comparison of the characteristics of FTAs and FAAs.

Table 1

A Juxtaposition of FTAs and FAAs

Face-Threatening Acts (FTAs)	Face-Attacking Acts (FAAs)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are not necessarily face-attacking • Rely on threat • Are bilateral (involve both self and other's face) • Threat is natural • Are void of self intentionality • Are void of motivation • Threat is inevitable • Other must be present • Do not entail legal prosecution • Are <i>a posteriori</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are also face-threatening • Rely on threat and attack • May be unilateral • Attack is intentional • Are ignited by self intentionality • Are fueled by motivation (ill or good) • Attack is avoidable • Other may be present • May entail legal prosecution • Are <i>a priori</i>

The threat in FTAs is quite natural. Any time an individual (i.e., self) starts some act that requires the cooperation of another individual (i.e., other), the self has to admit that they are imposing themselves on a property of other. For example, in an act of asking for direction, the self requires other to sacrifice some of their time and to donate some of their information while the self does not pay other for the service which they provide (unless we take

“thanks” as a kind of payment). The threat to face is bilateral in that the self is imposing their own wants on the face-wants of other and simultaneously lowering themselves by making a request. By way of contrast, the attack in FAAs is not natural; it does not start in and of itself. It requires fuel and ignition. Motivation is the fuel, and intention is the ignition. While the threat in an FTA starts only after the self has started to perform the FTA in question, the attack in an FAA has started even before the act itself starts; it has started in the mind of the self (e.g., as in holding ‘grudge’ for someone). As soon as the self makes up their mind and decides to perform the act, the attack has theoretically started although it may take some time to turn up in practice. By this token, it is even possible to put the intention of the self on a par with the attack of the FAA; intention is the theoretical counterpart of attack, and attack is the practical counterpart of intention.

It is the very intentional nature of FAAs that makes them avoidable. While the threat in FTAs comes about quite naturally, the attack in FAAs requires the active engagement of the self. The threat in FTAs simply occurs as a by-product or side-effect of performance; the self performs that act and the threat to both his own face and the other’s face ensues. In FAAs, on the other hand, the self makes the attack quite consciously and purposefully. The self is determined and motivated to make the attack; they choose to do so. If they did not, the attack would not occur. As such, the threat in an FTA is inevitable, but the attack in an FAA can be easily avoided. It only requires that the self extinguish their motivation and avoid their action. Nevertheless, this does not mean that the attack has not occurred. The ‘theoretical attack’ has occurred, but the self has actively decided to put the ‘practical attack’ on hold.

The motivation that fuels FAAs may be malignant or benign; ill motivation aims at causing intentional damage to the face-wants of other. In an act of gossiping, for example, the self intentionally performs the gossip act with the determination and motivation of vilifying other. The same is true of an act of slandering or stigmatizing. Good motivation, on the other hand, aims at stopping the train of ill-motivated attacks; it equips the self and/or other with a protective shield. Therefore, the FAA takes on a face-guarding responsibility; hence, Face-Guarding Acts (FGAs). The act of asking for explanation in the following scenario, for instance, is a Face Attacking Act (FAA) that involves good motivation and may be perceived as an FGA.

Dr Fereshteh has recently been too much of a nuisance than pleasure in the organization. She has been talking ill of several of her colleagues. On one occasion, she told several of her colleagues that Dr Mohammad, a colleague, had told her that Dr Hasan had told him that he would make

maximum use his power to stop Dr Fereshteh's job promotion. Neither Dr Mohammad nor Dr Hasan knew of this plot. A third party called on Dr Hasan and told him about the rumor. Dr Hasan summoned both Dr Mohammad and Dr Fereshteh to his office and confronted both of them to ask for a clear explanation.

In this scenario, there are two FAAs, one performed by Dr Fereshteh out of ill motivation (or maybe because of a habit of mind), and the other performed by Dr Hasan out of good will. Dr Fereshteh's spreading rumors behind his colleagues (i.e., slandering) is face-attacking in that it aims at encouraging others to accept that Dr Hasan is not a cooperative person, and that Dr Mohammad is not reticent. Such an act which has no job to do other than to attack the face-wants of Dr Mohammad and Dr Hasan is no doubt a face-attacking act, and the motivation is not anything other than sinister and noxious unless we accept that Dr Fereshteh is mentally ill, and that she requires medical attention. By way of contrast, the second FAA performed by Dr Hasan in this scenario is fueled by good will; it aimed at stopping the FAA being performed by Dr Fereshteh and the one(s) supposedly by Dr Mohammad.

Dr Hasan could have ignored what he had heard; in that case, he would not perform the FAA. He might of course become quite furious, develop bad feelings and nurture bad thoughts about both Dr Fereshteh and Dr Mohammad without ever deciding to perform the confrontation act. Alternatively, he might just stay relaxed and feel pity for both of them. This implies that FAAs require a certain degree of self intention if they want to be practically performed. It also implies that FAAs may start in the mind of the self on the theoretical thought plane (i.e., remain as thoughts and feelings) but never find their way into action on the practical action plane (i.e., become objective attacks) due to the hierarchical power-structure between the self and other, or the self's lack of confidence, his mental block, his personal preferences, or some other factor. In this scenario, Dr Hasan was the more powerful individual in the organization under whom both Dr Mohammad and Dr Fereshteh worked. It is quite easy to imagine what would happen if the organizational roles of Dr Fereshteh and Dr Hasan changed; the attack might lie dormant (in the form of grudge) in the mind of the agent.

The paradox in FAAs is that they can simultaneously be face-guarding. In the scenario above, the performed act attacks the face of the other parties, but at the same time it aims at guarding Dr Hasan's own face. Like FAAs, FGAs are intentional. In fact, the same act can be an FAA and an FGA simultaneously. It is like a half-empty mug of water which is perceived as half-full by some people; the choice as to which label (i.e., half-full versus half-empty) to use depends on the viewer's perspective or 'angle of view'. If a third party were

present in the above scenario, they might perceive Dr Hasan's act as being equally face attacking as they might call the act face guarding.

4. A Model for FAAs

The argumentation presented in section 3 vouches for the claim that FAAs are controlled at least by two factors: (1) self's intention, and (2) their Motivation or will. Figure 2 represents the interplay of these factors and provides some examples of FAAs/FGAs:

Figure 2. A hypothetical model for FAAs.

The model suggests that the self needs to have both the intention and the will or motivation to perform FAAs/FGAs. The model also suggests two planes for the action of the self: (a) the thought plane which is abstract, and (b) the action plane which is concrete and objective. These two planes are distinguished by the intensity of the self's intention and imply that the self's intention should reach a threshold level before thoughts (i.e., hypothetical actions) get transformed into (objective) actions. Will or motivation, on the other hand, is the factor that determines whether the attack hidden in an act assumes a destructive force or a protective/constructive one. The half-circle

that lies on the left in Figure 2 shows ill motivation whereas the one that lies on the right represents positive motivation. It is, therefore possible, to hypothesize four types of FAAs/FGAs: (1) self-destructive hypothetical FAAs, (2) self-/other-guarding hypothetical FGAs, (3) other-destructive objective FAAs, and (4) self-/other-guarding objective FGAs. These FAA/FGA types are in a sense first order notions because they are judgments about behavior. At the same time, they somehow deviate from the status of first order concepts as understood by Watts, Ide and Ehlich (1992) and also Eelen (2001) in that they are not simply judgments about the behavior of other; rather, they also embrace judgments about the behavior of the self; because they are being approached on a theoretical level here, they can also be considered as second order concepts (Locher and Watts, 2008).

Take grudge as an example. It is the function of self's ill will and their weak intention for objective action. The self has enough ill motivation to fuel an attack but due to some personal, psychological, social, or cultural reason fails to ignite and plunge the attack. Therefore, the attack already exists on the hypothetical thought plane but does not find the occasion to turn up into real objective concrete action. As such, its function becomes quite destructive to the self. By way of contrast, an act of gossip or slander is an FAA in which ill motivation provides the fuel for action and the self's intention is strong enough to reach beyond the threshold level to ignite objective action in the absence of other—but presence of a third party. Therefore, an act of gossip is an objective FAA which aims at attacking the face of other; hence, other-destructive. Along the same lines, when positive motivation or good will goes hand in hand with weak intention, passive self-and-other-guarding acts ensue. Here the self does not have any strong intention to ignite an objective FGA, but his motivation provides enough fuel for a dormant hypothetical FGA which aims at guarding both the self and the other. An example of such an FGA can be a 'feeling of pity' for other. However, if the intention grows strong enough to reach beyond the threshold level necessary for the objectification of the thought, the hypothetical FGA will find its way up and will surf on the action plane. Here the intention ignites the fuel provided by good will, and they go hand in hand to start an objective and concrete FGA. The job of such an FGA is to actively guard the self and other, and to do so by attacking other's face-wants. Asking for explanation, giving advice, confrontation, warning, and the like are acts that fit well into this class of FGAs.

Being behavioral in nature, FAAs/FGAs are controlled by a multitude of factors. In the confrontation example above, Dr Hasan was the vice president of the organization in which Dr Fereshteh and Dr Mohammad worked as regular employees. His authority, therefore, provided him with enough power and intention to objectify the FGA. Moreover, his strong religious values told him that the FGA had to be performed so that both his own face-wants and

the face-wants of the other parties involved in the event would be satisfied. It is paradoxical to see that Dr Hasan performs a face-attacking act whose function is simultaneously face-guarding; I therefore would like to suggest that FAA be used as an umbrella term for both FAAs and FGAs. It should also be noted that, in addition to authority and religious values, many other variables can control and manipulate FAAs/FGAs. The factors include self-control, self-esteem, mental block, shyness, intimidation, coercion, rudeness, rapport, ethics, culture, and emotions inter alia.

5. Rethinking (Im)politeness

The model presented above underscores the role and vitality of the self's intention in the objectification of FAAs. Motivation, on the other hand, plays a role in determining the constructive or destructive nature of FAAs. Now the question is whether the self's intention is in any way connected to (im)politeness. I intentionally evade using politeness/impoliteness and prefer to use (im)politeness instead to imply and emphasize that they are essentially the same. Before I discuss the implications of my model for a description of (im)politeness, I need to review what others have already said on the subject. A description of politeness was presented in section 2 above, so I just focus on a review of impoliteness here, and then discuss my own model in relation to (im)politeness.

A good number of (im)politeness researchers have emphasized the importance of the intentions of the self in discussions of politeness (cf., Lachenicht, 1980; Austin, 1990; Hickey, 1991; Beebe, 1995; Culpeper, 1996; Kienpointner, 1997; Harris, 2001; Culpeper, Bousfield and Wichmann, 2003; Culpeper, 2005; Mills, 2005; Rudanko, 2006; Bousfield, 2007a, b). For one thing, Bousfield (2008) magnified the role of self's intentions in his definition of impoliteness which assumes that impoliteness constitutes the "issuing of intentionally gratuitous and conflictive face-threatening acts (FTAs) that are purposefully performed" (Bousfield, 2008, p. 132)—with which I do not agree because some insane and mad people may issue such FTAs without being labeled *impolite*. Culpeper, too, conceived that agent's intentionality (i.e., the self's intention) plays a major role in impolite acts, and that impoliteness involves acts that (a) intend to cause other's loss of face or that (b) are perceived by other to have such intention (Culpeper, 2008). As such, both Bousfield (2008) and Culpeper (2008) argue that other's understanding and realization of the self's intention is the key to impoliteness. On the other hand, Terkourafi (2008) assumes that such realization and understanding by the other constitutes what she calls 'rudeness' rather than impoliteness. For Terkourafi, "*impoliteness* occurs when the expression used is not

conventionalised relative to the context of occurrence; it threatens the addressee's face (and, through that, the speaker's face) but no face-threatening intention is attributed to the speaker by the hearer" (2008, p. 70). Along the same lines, Locher and Watts (2008, p. 79) note that:

Negatively marked behavior, i.e. behavior that has breached a social norm . . . , evokes negative evaluations such as *impolite* or *over-polite* (or any alternative lexeme such as *rude*, *aggressive*, *insulting*, *sarcastic*, etc. depending upon the degree of the violation and the type of conceptualization the inappropriate behavior is profiled against).

The phrase 'negative evaluations' in this quotation implies what has come to be known in the literature on (im)politeness as the 'relational aspects of communication' defined as the overt or tacit attempts of social actors at negotiating their positions in relation to each other. The term 'relational work' has been used to refer to "all aspects of the work invested by individuals in the construction, maintenance, reproduction and transformation of interpersonal relationships among those engaged in social practice" (Locher and Watts, 2008, p. 96). As such, anything that has to do with interpersonal relations falls within the category of relational work. Returning to my model in section 4 above (Figure 2), it appears that only the behavior observed on the action plane is a kind of relational work, and that any thought which lies dormant on the abstract thought plane is not—or at least I assume, based on the phrases 'work' and 'social practice' in the above quotation from Locher and Watts (2008) that they are reserving 'relational work' for the action plane. They just see the tip of the iceberg. If this is what they want to suggest, I should admit that their conclusion is short-sighted when we notice, for instance, that grudge—which falls on the thought plane—has the power to cut off an interpersonal relation.

To me it seems that a precise definition of (im)politeness requires a distinction between 'individual pragmatic competence', and 'collective pragmatic competence'. To me, it seems that each culturally-unique human population has developed certain values over centuries that inform correct forms of social behavior and public/interpersonal speech, and that a majority of individuals in the same population have been brought up to know and respect these values. The "shared knowledge of correct forms of social behavior and of public/interpersonal speech" is what I would like to call "Collective Pragmatic Competence" or CPC. It appears that CPC is population-specific in that what is considered a correct form of speech or behavior by one human population may be considered incorrect by another even within the same cultural milieu. As such, CPC is a component of culture in the formation of which literature, education, religion, and many other factors have played an historical role.

Figure 3. Model for (im)politeness.

For one thing, the Iranian society has a two-thousand-plus-year-old Zoroastrians tradition of upholding ‘good thoughts’, ‘good words’, and ‘good deeds’ at the heart of its value system¹, and there are certain terms and adjectives in Persian that label any human act, speech, or thought in accordance with these principle values and virtues. The Persian words and phrases that I used in the introduction to this paper are just a few examples.

Anyway, accepting the existence of CPC as an institutional fact (c.f., Searle, 1995) at an abstract level implies that it will be possible to base judgments about (im)politeness on CPC. What needs to be done is to give descriptions of samples of speech and behavior to a human population to label. This is just what I did. I prepared precise descriptions of instances of social speech, interpersonal speech, and social behavior, and then asked people to label them. The model for (im)politeness that I have presented in Figure 3 (above) is based on the data I collected in this way.

The model clearly marks the borders of (im)politeness. It suggests that politeness pertains to speech or to a context in which both speech and deeds exist provided that speech is dominant and deeds are recess, just like in biology where recess genes give in to dominant genes. Politeness is therefore a quality of an individual’s *verbal behavior*, not a quality of his deeds; the more appropriate term for deeds is conduct. The dotted line in the model marks the border between thought plain and action plane. When thought is not externalized, it lies dormant on the thought plain, but it may assume such identities as optimism, hope, jealousy, hatred, pessimism, grudge, fear, and so forth. However, when thought is externalized, it surfaces on the action plane and assumes either of the three identities: (a) speech/words, (b) deeds/action/behavior, or (c) act-speech (i.e., speech accompanied by deeds).

It should be noted that sometimes thoughts get automatically externalized with the self having no control over them and no intention to surface them. A mentally-retarded person, for instance, may talk or act in socially-unacceptable terms, but no one considers it as impoliteness or rudeness. Therefore, other’s perception or knowledge of the self’s intentions, informed decision, motivation, cultural background, and psycho-somatic health (inter alia) is the key factor to determining which label to use for the self’s externalized thought. The model suggests that politeness be redefined as:

¹ The picture of Iran projected through international mass media is not a real picture, and the few people (especially politicians) who are seen by the world do not represent the people of Iran—most of them are not Iranian by origin.

The quality as perceived by other, a third party, or both of speech which is suitable to the context and to other, and which is intentionally uttered by the normal healthy conscious self in the context where speech is dominant.

By the same token, impoliteness can be redefined as:

The quality as perceived by other, a third party, or both of speech which is unsuitable to the context and other, and which is intentionally uttered by the normal healthy conscious self in the context where speech is dominant.

The definition of impoliteness presented here is somewhat different from the one presented by Locher and Watts who maintain that “*Impoliteness is behavior that is face-aggravating in a particular context*” (2008, p. 3). Their definition is blind to a number of factors. First, their definition does not distinguish between speech and behavior and uses the label ‘impoliteness’ for behavior as well. Second, it does not underscore the role of other’s interpretation or that of a third part. Moreover, it does not take the health, intentions, and other qualities of the self into account. As such, any definition like the one by Locher and Watts (2008), or the ones presented at the beginning of this section, will undoubtedly result in confusion.

It should be noted that where there is speech, there are FTAs or FAAs. It is the third party or other that decides whether the self has performed an FTA or an FAA, and whether the self has been conscious, normal, and healthy or not; it is the third party or other that decides whether speech is suitable to other and the context or not, and whether speech is dominant or not. An example is in order here:

Farhad, a university professor, is invited to join a party where some of his friends are invited too. He joins the party along with his wife, Tayebbeh. Upon arriving at the party venue, friends greet him asking:

A FRIEND: *Welcome. How are you? Are you having a good time?*

FARHAD: *Oh thanks. I am OK. Actually, I feel as if I am in Heaven even when I am in Hell provided that Tayebbeh is with me.*

Upon hearing this response, some of the other ladies present at the party turn to their husbands and say:

WOMEN: *Learn from Farhad; look how he is complimenting and*

praising his wife.

At this time, Tayebah gets furious and complains:

TAYEBEH: *You don't know this man; he did not compliment me. He insulted me; he means I am much worse than Hell, so much so that when he goes to Hell with me, Hell is like heaven for him when it is compared to me.*

This is an authentic example which clearly shows how an utterance assumes different readings and interpretations based on interpersonal context. While Farhad's utterance looks like a compliment to the third party present in the context, it is taken as an insult by Tayebah. Farhad's speech achieves different effects on different listeners. Tayebah takes it as an impolite act while the third party takes it as a polite one. If asked what his intention was, Farhad might simply respond "I was just kidding." Therefore, in this single example, three different readings of Farhad's intention have been counted. CPC would have it that the reading counted by the third party is the default unmarked reading, and that Farhad's speech was polite. What I would like to suggest here is that from the interpersonal perspective, other's use of their own individual pragmatic competence for the evaluation of the self is invalid for labeling the self as (im)polite; it does not *make* the self (im)polite. The label does not stick to the self. It is CPC that works as a powerful adhesive glue which attaches the label 'impolite' to the self.

Paradoxically, sometimes even a failure on the part of the self to verbally respond to the requirements of the context reads as impoliteness. In other words, when the context by its very nature recommends that speech accompany action, the self will be labeled impolite if they fail to provide the required speech or simply evade it. This flouts Grice's maxim of quantity (Grice, 1957). Here, other considers the evasion to be intentional. An example is in order here:

Dr Mohsen is a university professor. One day, on his way to the vice chancellor's office, he runs into the chancellor of the university. They stop to greet each other, and at the same time the chancellor's secretary passes by carrying to the chancellor's office a tray full of fruits. The chancellor reaches the tray, picks up a banana, peels it, and starts eating, but extends no ostensible invitation to Dr Mohsen to have a banana.

Knowing that an ostensible invitation is a *must* in this scenario is part of the CPC of Iranian speakers of Persian. The chancellor's evasion of the ostensible invitation runs counter to the requirements of the setting. His action (picking

up the banana) *must have been* accompanied by speech (extending an ostensible invitation to Dr Mohsen to pick up one). The setting was such that speech was culturally dominant, and action recess, but the chancellor attempted to make action dominant in the setting—an attempt which was doomed to failure. As such, impoliteness involves both the presence of speech—in addition to its appropriateness—where it should not be present, and its absence where it should not be absent.

In another example, the setting was such that it did not require any speech, but the self uttered his impoliteness.

A group of six university professors were sitting in a row on an Airbus plane flying from Tehran to Bushehr. The two persons sitting in the window seats on both ends of the same row of seats were strangers. Knowing Dr Habib, one of the six professors, the flight person waited on the row with an exceptional round of cappuccino (which is not part of the normal courtesy on Iranian domestic flights). Dr Ahmad, one of the university professors, called the two strangers sitting in the window seats and said:

Dr Ahmad: *Hey guys, you know what? Remember any time you want an exceptional round of cappuccino on a plane, just sit in the same row with Dr Habib.*

This was an act of utter impoliteness and created acute embarrassment for Dr Habib who instantly addressed the strangers and said:

Dr Habib: *I do apologize to you both, I am so sorry for Dr Ahmad's comment. I am really belittled.*

In this context, no one was supposed to utter anything addressed to the two strangers other than phatic talk (c.f., Malinowski, 1923). Dr Ahmad's speech was pointless because it was neither an ice-breaker nor an instance of phatic communion; it simply caused acute embarrassment. In this context, behavior/deed was to be the only element, and if any speech was to be made at all, it would undoubtedly be recess to action which was dominant. Dr Ahmad's wrong computation of the elements of context resulted in his uttering his own impoliteness. The individual pragmatic competences of the university professors in the row would, of course, indicate that Dr Ahmad's comment was habitual, but the individual pragmatic competences of the two strangers, as well as those of the people I interviewed for this study, clearly marked Dr Ahmad's speech as sarcastic—and therefore impolite. In other

words, CPC would accept the impolite label for his comment.

6. Conclusion

Most of the discussion presented in this paper was made from a theoretical point of view and was—to borrow a term from Locher and Watts (2008, p. 5)—the product of a ‘second-order’ conceptualization. Nevertheless, first-order concepts (i.e., judgments about behavior) were also employed in this paper; the first-order concepts (e.g., polite, impolite, foolishness, and so on) employed in the paper informed the line of argumentation I adopted for my discussion.

All in all, this paper argued that FTA, (im)politeness, and several other terms commonly seen in (im)politeness literature are quite fuzzy. The argument presented in the paper led to the introduction of a new class of FTAs called Face Attacking Acts (FAAs). It also suggested revised definitions for politeness and impoliteness. It was argued that human use of language takes place on the abstract thought plane as well as on the concrete action plane, and suggested that motivation (be it ill will or good will) is the fuel for action and that self’s intention is the ignition that can push thoughts that lie dormant at the base of the action iceberg to move towards the tip. The paper also has implications for psycho-pragmatics.

Needless to say, language is not always produced in spoken form. People also make use of language to write text. My study concluded that writing is different from speech in politeness terms. My interview corpus revealed that, when asked to label writing, interviewees did not use the polite/impolite dichotomy. Rather, they preferred to evaluate writing as a deed and therefore labeled writing the way they labeled self’s non-verbal behavior. This is quite interesting in that deed is considered dominant in writing although language is the main element of writing. In other words, although language is the key agent that brings written performance into existence, it is considered as the recess element in writing. As such, people do not use the same labels they use for speakers to express their evaluations of writers when they produced the same language. It seems as if people see written performance as a product of some deed, not a product of language or speech. Nevertheless, people distinguished between writing produced for communication (e.g., Emails, Mails, etc.) and writing produced for entertainment (e.g., poems, novels, etc.). While they confidently used labels for the evaluation of writers who had produced communicative pieces of written text, they were not confident in their labeling of authors who had produced entertaining texts. This is a quite interesting phenomenon and requires further research not only in Persian but also in other languages.

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